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Saturday Breakfast

American soldiers,
Troopers and officials,
Gathered at dawn.
In the mess tent:
Reading bulk of mails,
Sipping news from prints,
Stood unarmed with hangover.

Prisoners in sibley tents,
Unfed overnight.
In the town's plaza,
Without warning:
Church bells rang
In startling suddenness,
"Atake, Balangigan-on."